

D6.2 Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Activities

Date: January 23, 2024

Document Identification			
Status	Final	Due Date	31/12/2023
Version	1.0	Submission Date	23/01/2024

Related WP	WP6	Document Reference	D6.2
Related Deliverable(s)	D6.1	Dissemination Level (*)	PU
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Keywords:
Dissemination, communication, branding, social media, website, blog posts

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This document is issued within the frame and for the purpose of the HiDALGO2 project. Funded by the European Union. This work has received funding from the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) and Poland, Germany, Spain, Hungary, France under grant agreement number: 101093457. This publication expresses the opinions of the authors and not necessarily those of the EuroHPC JU and Associated Countries which are not responsible for any use of the information contained in this publication. **This deliverable is subject to final acceptance by the European Commission.** This document and its content are the property of the HiDALGO2 Consortium. The content of all or parts of this document can be used and distributed provided that the HiDALGO2 project and the document are properly referenced.

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Document History			
Version	Date	Change editors	Changes
0.1	13/12/2023	FN	Table of contents. Main structure and content of the document.
0.2	18/12/2023	FN	Application of changes proposed by the first reviewer.
0.3	22/12/2023	FN	Application of changes proposed by the quality manager.
0.4	12/01/2024	FN	Application of changes proposed by the first reviewer.
0.5	17/01/2024	FN	Application of changes proposed by the second reviewer.
0.7	21/01/2024	FN	Application of changes proposed by the quality manager.
1.0	23/01/2024	PSNC	FINAL VERSION TO BE SUBMITTED

Quality Control		
Role	Who (Partner short name)	Approval Date
Deliverable leader	Kyriaki Daskaloudi (FN)	17/01/2024
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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation/ acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CoE	Centre of Excellence
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EuroHPC JU	EuroHPC Joint Undertaking
HPC	High Performance Computing
HPDA	High Performance Data Analytics
PU	Public
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
WP	Work Package
WP6	Work Package 6

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a report on the HiDALGO2 project's dissemination and communication activities that aim to raise awareness among the industrial and research community, disseminate innovative project results to various communities of the HPC, HPDA, and AI and interact with related groups. The report serves as a comprehensive document outlining the implemented activities based on the strategy and tools presented in the D6.1 "Brand and Roadmap for Awareness Campaign" and describes their results in reaching the HiDALGO2's target audience and objectives. The activities include a combination of synchronous (conferences, participation in events, etc.) and asynchronous approaches (newsletters, social media tactics, etc.).

The report includes updates of the plans outlined in D6.1 "Brand and Roadmap for Awareness Campaign" which are continuously under monitoring and revisioning throughout the project's duration to ensure maximum impact.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to review in detail the performance of the Hidalgo2 project on the specific communication and dissemination activities and the progress regarding the KPIs - as described in the D6.1 “Brand and Roadmap for Awareness Campaign” - in a complete report. The review considers the period between the start of the HiDALGO2 project in January 2023 (M01) until December 2023 (M12) and includes updates on the communication and dissemination strategy, like the new campaigns planned for social media to increase impact through our social media channels.

1.2 Relation to other project work

The results of the dissemination, communication, and Clustering Activities, as part of Task 6.5 “Project Branding, Dissemination and Communication” are closely related to several other tasks and deliverables of the project, as described below:

- Task 2.3 “Dashboard and Service Offering” and related Deliverable D2.3 “HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services”: They are both closely connected with tasks from WP6 on community building.
- Task 4.3 “Artificial Intelligence for Global Challenges” and related Deliverable D4.2 “Advances in HPDA and AI for Global Challenges”: This task supports the pilot applications developed in WP5 and the supportive actions in WP6 using Artificial Intelligence (AI).
- Task 4.5 “Coupling Technologies” and related Deliverable D4.1 “Data Management and Coupling Technologies”: This task’s activity goes across work packages WP2 to WP6, where infrastructure and development services are involved.
- WP5 “Tackling Global Challenges” (includes all the work related to the use cases): The results of this entire WP will be a significant part of the project’s dissemination since it will be of great interest to external stakeholders.
- Task 6.3 “Expanding Competences by Trainings”: it is aiming to collect and share knowledge, best practices, available resources and mechanisms for appliances, applications and software frameworks for tackling the identified Global Challenges with HPC and AI and is going to be a significant part of the project’s communications and dissemination activities targeted to external stakeholders.
- Task 6.4 “Awareness Creation, Collaboration and Community Support”: It is a task identifying and engaging a broader HiDALGO2 stakeholder community and national and international projects around the world that are related to HiDALGO2. It is expected to significantly contribute to reaching the communication goals.

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- Deliverable D6.1 “Brand and Roadmap for Awareness Campaign”: It provides the tools and guidelines to the Hidalgo2 consortium to contribute to the communication and dissemination activities.

Finally, WP6 aims to promote a sustainable operation of the Centre of Excellence, fostering communication and dissemination activities including training, workshops, collaboration with other projects and organizations and demonstrating the HiDALGO2 results to the general public.

1.3 Structure of the document

Following the introduction, the document is structured in 6 major chapters except the introduction (Chapter 1).

Chapter 2 presents the dissemination, communication & clustering activities for the past year, explaining the division between communication and dissemination activities.

Chapter 3 includes the report on external communication, providing details on the progress of the press release publications.

Chapter 4 includes the report on dissemination activities using online tools, like the website, blog posts, newsletter, social media, and communication on other platforms.

Chapter 5 includes the report on the off-line dissemination activities, like the creation and distribution of printed promotional materials in conferences and training, the publications of articles in scientific journals and popular science media, and the collaborations and synergies with other projects, initiatives, and bodies.

Chapter 6 includes the collaborations and synergies that were planned as well as the ones that the project completed in the past 12 months.

Chapter 7 describes the conclusions, including the challenges faced and the corrective actions and next steps to be taken by the consortium that ensure the success of the project's Dissemination and Communication goals.

In the **Annex**, the reader will find a table with all the KPIs report.

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2. Dissemination, Communication & Clustering Activities Report

All project partners have contributed to the communication and dissemination activities. The contribution of each partner has varied based on their nature and the intended audience, both in terms of content and type. The industrial partners, namely ATOS, MeteoGrid and the High-Performance Computing Center Stuttgart (HLRS), approached relevant standardization and regulatory bodies, industry sectors, as well as their distributors and client network. The academic and research partners mainly focused on disseminating the project results to research institutes and universities. The academic partners namely are the Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC), the Centre for Modeling and Simulation in Strasbourg (Cemosis), the Institute of Communications and Computer Systems (ICCS) and the Széchenyi István University (SZE). Such activities prepare the creation of an active community capable of understanding the extent and importance of the project’s solutions and adopting them at later stages.

This chapter reports on the implementation of the dissemination and communication strategy of the HiDALGO2 project and presents the main paths followed. There is a very close relationship between dissemination (spreading knowledge, see Section 2.2), communication (building awareness and promoting, see Section 2.1), and clustering activities (community building, see Section 6). HiDALGO2 aims to primarily disseminate results such as data, models, use cases, scientific or technical papers, etc. and works to have open communication channels with its stakeholders, allowing two-way communication and actively receiving feedback from the community when required.

The HiDALGO2 project activities differentiated between two major strands of communication and dissemination:

- (i) the general promotion/communication activities, which were focused mainly on the first months of the project, targeting the wide public audience (mainly through the communication channels of the project), and
- (ii) a set of more specific activities, dissemination activities, dedicated to the presentation of HiDALGO2 advances and outcomes to the scientific communities, academia, and industries (through dissemination means).

These dissemination activities become more important as the project evolves and concrete results become the focus of the project’s activities.

In the below sections, it is described how and to what extent the HiDALGO2 dissemination activities have spread awareness of the project and its results to the audience within the scientific and research community.

The procedures and tools for producing, reviewing, and publishing communication content are thoroughly described in the D6.1. correspondent section (3.4)

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2.1 Communication activities

Several communication initiatives, including establishing a project website, publishing regular newsletters and blogs regarding the project progress, and maintaining social media accounts, have been carried out to increase the visibility of the HiDALGO2 project, as detailed in sections 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, and 4.4 of this report. The communication activities are focused on participating in public engagement activities to ensure that research and innovation activities are made known to professionals as well as the society at large, as detailed in section 5.3 and 6. In addition, a press release presenting the project’s scope and vision has been uploaded on the project website and is foreseen to be published during January 2024 in local and European media and spread on social media to communicate the results further, as detailed in section 3.1. Additionally, articles related to the project will be published in European journals and on all partners’ websites as well as on the project’s website, as detailed in sections 4.1, 4.5, 4.6, and 4.7.

2.2 Dissemination & Clustering Activities

Dissemination is focused on transferring knowledge and results to the target audience (including the research community, industry, policymakers, etc.) to enable others to use and take up results. The means used are defined by the type of knowledge to transfer. Dissemination activities are focused on participating in conferences/seminars/events, as detailed in section 5.3 presenting technologies and/ or papers, as detailed in section 5.2, organizing workshops and synergizing with other projects or organizations, as detailed in sections 5.3 and 6. The HiDALGO2 consortium members have participated in 11 conferences/events and have organized a workshop to be held in February at the HiPEAC Conference (see section 5.3). No clustering activities have been organized yet by the Hidalgo2 project.

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3. Communication Activities

3.1 Press Releases

HiDALGO2 has published a press release (1) announcing the project and will publish at least one more, aiming to gain publicity and raise public awareness. All project press releases are to be published on the project’s website and shared with popular media outlets in all partners’ countries, as listed in section 4.5 of the D6.1 “Brand and Roadmap for Awareness Campaign”. All the partners are requested to publish the press releases on their respective websites and social media accounts.

RELEASE DATE: DECEMBER 2023 | 1st Press Release of the HiDALGO2 Project

EU research addresses climate and social phenomena with High Performance Computing

Climate change affects our everyday lives and, as a result, increasingly affects our life quality. One of the key reasons is the dynamic development of societies, which has had a significant impact on the natural environment for decades. This can be dramatically experienced nowadays through violent weather phenomena (e.g. storms, rainfall, fires) or the air quality in cities. The way we propose to deal with its impact is through an interdisciplinary approach and expertise which will enable better understanding and preparation of remedial strategies.

Figure 1. Press release on the website

The first press release presenting the project’s scope and vision is uploaded on the project’s website and is planned to be shared on the project’s social media channels and distributed in local and European media at the beginning of 2024.

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4. Online dissemination tools

4.1 Website

The project’s website is connected to a domain and is live at www.hidalgo2.eu. The content of the website is continuously updated, reviewed, and approved by all the consortium members, as well as shared through social media channels, to increase the website’s visibility and inform the community on topics related to the project and the industry. Social media campaigns (see section 4.4) linked to the website are also expected to increase traffic on the website.

Figure 2. Website landing page

The content uploaded is provided by the consortium and managed and edited by the Dissemination leaders (FN). The website's updated content is uploaded in the correspondent sections, (as presented in Table 2 in D6.1) and includes:

- All the news about the activities of the HiDALGO2 project and the related events that the HiDALGO2 consortium members participated in
- Papers and other publications related to the project
- Newsletters and press releases
- A Blog section and section with the latest blog articles on the homepage

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Figure 3. Website unique visitors & views

The targeted KPI for the website is to have 8000 unique visitors by the end of the project. **By December 2023 (M12), the website has 666 unique visitors.** It is expected that the rate towards achieving this KPI will increase as more results will be shared on the webpage and promoted on social media channels as the project advances.

Something worth mentioning is that our LinkedIn page is the top social media channel to direct visitors to our website. This observation can be explained by the fact that the project’s LinkedIn page is the one followers interact the most with, compared to Facebook and Twitter (see section 4.4.1.).

4	Referrer ▶	Referrer Type ▶	Visitors ▼	Views ▶	Session Duration ▶	Bounce Rate
1	LinkedIn ↗	Social	46 (64.79%)	70 (67.31%)	3:44	78%
2	Twitter ↗	Social	13 (18.31%)	14 (13.46%)	0:11	92%
3	Facebook ↗	Social	12 (16.90%)	18 (17.31%)	0:41	77%
4	GitHub ↗	Social	2 (2.82%)	2 (1.92%)	-	100%

Figure 4. Website analytics

4.2. Blog posts

One blog post has been published on the website every month, starting in Month 2. All partners contribute to this task, following a rotation plan that can be found in the shared drive folder of the project. Reminders are sent by the Dissemination leader (FN) when the delivery time is close and when not met. The published blog articles delivered by the

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partners and published on the website are listed below in Table 1. **Eight blog posts were published by December 2023 (M12).**

Table 1. Blog Posts

Blog Issue	Release Month	Title	Contributor
1st	M2 (February 2023)	HiDALGO2 Project Started (2)	FN
2nd	M3 (March 2023)	HiDALGO2 – EXCELLERAT P2 joint mini symposium at the SIAM CSE23 conference (3)	SZE
3rd	M5 (May 2023)	Meet the HiDALGO2 partner Cemosis: Strasbourg Modeling and Simulation Center (4)	UNISTRA/CEMOSIS
4th	M6 (June 2023)	The QCG-portal and HiDALGO2 (5)	PSNC
5th	M7 (July 2023)	Uncertainty Quantification in HiDALGO2: Enhancing Modeling Credibility for Environmental Pilots (6)	HLRS
6th	M8 (August 2023)	Trying to decode the wildfires' behaviour (7)	ICCS
7th	M10 (October 2023)	Data analytics, AI, and visualisation in the HiDALGO2 project (8)	FN
8th	M10 (October 2023)	HiDALGO2 Adopts DevOps and CI/CD for Seamless Supercomputer Deployments (9)	Collaborative

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4.3. Newsletters

Welcome from the Project Coordinator

Dear Readers of the newsletter, Colleagues,

The HiDALGO2 project is an important undertaking for European science addressing important key challenges for the entire international community, namely climate change. They have long been an undeniable phenomenon observed in many

Figure 5. Newsletter Banner and Welcome Note

The project released two HiDALGO2 newsletters, which are made available to the public through the project's website and actively promoted on HiDALGO2 social media accounts, as detailed in D6.1. Users have the option to either read the newsletters online or download.

The first and second Newsletters have been published on the website. (10) (11)

The first and second Newsletters have been published on LinkedIn. (12) (13)

The first and second Newsletters have been published on X (Twitter). (14) (15)

The first and second Newsletters have been published on Facebook. (16) (17)

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The targeted KPIs are: 12 newsletters in total, 300 individuals/ organizations signed up to receive newsletters by December 2024 (M24) and at least 600 total by December 2026 (M48). **By December 2023 (M12) we have published 2 newsletters and 58 people have subscribed to the project’s newsletter.** The newsletter plan has been updated and aligned with the internal activities of the project (see Table 2). As mentioned above our goal is to publish 12 newsletters by the end of the project, and we expect more people to subscribe as we share the project’s results on the website’s news section and through the newsletters.

Table 2. Newsletter publication updated plan.

Newsletter Issue	Release Month	Content Submission by	Published
1 st	M4 (April 2023)	31.03.23	31.05.23
2 nd	M9 (September 2023)	31.08.23	31.10.23
3 rd	M13 (January 2024)	15.01.24	N/A
4 th	M17 (May 2024)	15.05.24	N/A
5 th	M21 (September 2024)	15.09.24	N/A
6 th	M24 (December 2024)	15.12.24	N/A

4.4. Social Media

HiDALGO2 is present in key popular social media networks as described in the D6.1 Brand and Roadmap for Awareness Campaign. Specifically, the HiDALGO2 project maintains active social media accounts on X (Twitter), LinkedIn, Facebook, and YouTube, which have been in use since February 2023. Their accounts on each social media platform are the following:

- X (Twitter): @HiDALGO2_EU (18)
- LinkedIn: HiDALGO2 Project (19)
- YouTube: @HiDALGO2, (20)
- Facebook: Hidalgo2 EU Project (21)

The HiDALGO2 social media posts actively promote project news, share information about partners' participation in dissemination activities, and provide links to corresponding details on the project's webpage.

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Within HiDALGO2, partners contribute to social media posts based on a rotation plan outlined in D6.1. Future Needs oversees post editing and management to uphold the social media profiles. The partners and Future Needs, as the dissemination leader, have identified influencers to follow, while accounts which do not qualify as influencers but are still a worthy source of information have been added to the respective X (Twitter) lists.

The number of posts requested by the partners to be posted weekly remains as set at the beginning of the project, based on best practices for profile maintenance:

- 9 tweets per week (2 HiDALGO2 project promotion tweets, 7 re-tweets)
- LinkedIn/Facebook posts per week (1 HiDALGO2 project promotion post, 2 general relevant content posts)

The partners address the recommended number of posts published per week, aligning their contributions with their activities and updates on industry news. As of September 2023, some corrective actions were taken to improve performance. In addition to following the rotation plan, the consortium is encouraged to share ad hoc posts. The Future Needs Dissemination Team also creates complementary posts by sharing sector news found in the feed of the project's social media profiles. During the regular meeting, a report on the project's performance on social media is shared with the partners. They are also encouraged by email, to engage with the most popular social media posts of the project (with links provided) on all channels. The increasing rate of social media followers has confirmed that these actions are fruitful and are to be continued.

Social media KPIs target over 5000+ likes on all social media channels and involve at least 5 other projects in various online campaigns. **By December 2023 (M12) the HiDALGO2 project had garnered a total of 1975 likes on LinkedIn and X (Twitter) pages. No social media campaigns have started yet.** The targets per specific channel are mentioned in the 4.4.1 section below. See the annex for the full KPIs Table (Table 6).

Besides sharing the project's results as the activities of all Work Packages move on, focusing on community building in the upcoming years is anticipated to significantly boost the online networking of associated projects and initiatives.

Moreover, in the following months starting from January 2024 (M13) until the end of the project, a series of campaigns will start running on the social media pages of HiDALGO2 as a strategic tool to increase traffic on the project's channels. In particular, the campaigns planned for the next year include:

1. Joint actions with other relevant projects or organizations.
2. Meet the team, presenting the consortium team members and their role in the project.
3. Quizzes and polls on the technologies and science behind HiDALGO2.

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4.4.1. HiDALGO2 social media accounts analysis

4.4.1.1. X (former Twitter)

X (Twitter) is one of the main communication channels of the project. It is mainly used to post the latest updates and post “in-real time” during the project’s events and participation in activities.

Figure 6. X account followers

Social media KPIs target over 1000 X followers. By December 2023 (M12) the HiDALGO2 X profile has 434 followers.

The two most outstanding months of the year in terms of impressions and increase in followers were June and July 2023 (M6 and M7). Top posts are related to important conferences and webinars of the sector. More details can be seen below in Figures 7 and 8. To increase followers on X, the project will run social media campaigns and build a community of stakeholders, to engage more people and organizations with HiDALGO2.

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Jun 2023 · 30 days

POST HIGHLIGHTS

Top Tweet earned 534 impressions

🔪 A Monday #throwback look to the @ISChpc High Performance Conference 2023!
 🙌 We were glad to be part of this great #HPC "family"!
 #exascale
 #supercomputers
 twitter.com/EuroHPC_JU/sta...

🔄 1 ❤️ 10

View Tweet activity

View all Tweet activity

Top mention earned 18 engagements

💡 We had such a fruitful meeting with @EuroCC_Sweden and the company SLB-analys, associated with the @CityofSthlm. We made an introduction to the @HiDALGO2_EU project and a presentation of the Urban Air Pilot use case. We got great feedback and a proposal for further cooperation pic.twitter.com/ezuVYTzqWK

🔄 1 🗨️ 2 ❤️ 9

View Tweet activity

View all Tweet activity

JUN 2023 SUMMARY

Posts
45

Post impressions
4,677

Profile visits
2,501

Mentions
17

New followers
10

Figure 7. Hidalgo2 X account June analytics

Jul 2023 · 31 days

POST HIGHLIGHTS

Top Tweet earned 286 impressions

Do not miss on 7th July this interesting webinar about the #exascale era! twitter.com/Cheese_CoE/sta...

🔄 3 ❤️ 7

View Tweet activity

View all Tweet activity

Top mention earned 11 engagements

📢 In @HiDALGO2_EU, we work on a use case for #renewable #energy sources. Our partner @HLRS_HPC is involved in further projects dealing with #renewables, e.g. the WindHPC project. hls.de/news/detail/co...

@HPCWE_project
 @EuroHPC_JU
 @EUScienceInnov
 @Etp4HPC
 @EuroHPC pic.twitter.com/soi9qpMn0v

🔄 1 🗨️ 2 ❤️ 7

JUL 2023 SUMMARY

Posts
21

Post impressions
2,965

Profile visits
306

Mentions
4

New followers
3

Figure 8. Hidalgo2 X account July analytics

4.4.1.2. LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the most engaging communication channel the project uses to reach out to its audience. Due to the media’s nature, it is used mostly to reach out to professionals and

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academia. To increase followers on LinkedIn, the project will run social media campaigns to engage more people and organizations with HiDALGO2.

Figure 9. LinkedIn account

Social media KPIs target over 1500 LinkedIn followers. **By December 2023 (M12) the HiDALGO2 LinkedIn profile has 224 followers.** Below, some highlights from LinkedIn impressions and interaction with the HiDALGO2 page are presented.

Figure 10. LinkedIn analytics

In Figure 10, there is a graph representing the followers' interaction with the page throughout the year. The peak for the project's LinkedIn page, in terms of impressions and increase of followers, was recent, in November 2023 (M11), while the lower engagement is observed during the holiday seasons in Europe - less in Easter, more in the summer and the end of the year. Observing the intermediate peaks of the diagram we see there is a steady increase of the audience reach as the project advances. In a more detailed analysis,

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we identified that the line rises in the months with the most posts and with the most increased presence of the consortium members in the industry events (ex. November). It is planned that as the project advances more research results and scientific publications will be shared, which is expected to further increase the pace of the growth of the audience. The campaigns to be launched as mentioned in section 4.4 and the community of stakeholders that the project is building are going to further contribute to this, engaging more projects.

As mentioned before, our LinkedIn page is the top social media channel to link visitors to our website (Figure 4), implying that the most interested users are those active on LinkedIn.

4.4.1.3. Facebook

Facebook is another communication channel that the project is using. Even though it was not foreseen in the project Grant Agreement, it was created to share updates and reach to different user groups, potentially interested in the project activities or results. **By December 2023 (M12) the HiDALGO2 Facebook profile had 53 followers.**

Figure 11. Facebook account

Below, some highlights from Facebook page impressions and interaction with the HiDALGO2 page are presented. The peak for the project’s Facebook page, in terms of impressions and increase of followers, was February 2023 (M02).

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Figure 12. Facebook analytics

In Figure 12, the graph represents the number of Facebook users that our posts reached in the past year. It is visible that the posts reach peaks on specific dates. At the end of February for example, the project attended the Conference on Computational Science and Engineering and managed to reach almost 200 users through 2 reposts. Other peaks are mostly concerning events attended or organized by HiDALGO2. To increase followers on Facebook, the project will run social media campaigns and build a community of stakeholders, to engage more people and organizations with HiDALGO2.

4.4.1.4. YouTube

The YouTube channel of the Hidalgo2 project, is used to post project videos ensuring that they reach interested parties. The content of the channel is shared on the project’s website and other social media channels. **23 videos are shared and 26 people have subscribed.** No KPIs are set for this channel as no KPIs are related to videos produced during the project. However, the analytics show that subscribers increased as the channel was promoted among the consortium network and as new videos were added. Opportunities to reshare the existing content or share new videos created will increase traffic.

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Figure 13. YouTube account and posts

4.5. Partners' websites

Partners in the HiDALGO2 project promote its results and use cases on their website and through national and international communities and institutions. Below are the HiDALGO2 pages on the consortium partner's websites.

Table 3. HiDALGO2 in Partners' website

1. INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK (PSNC) (22)	PL Coordinator
2. HIGH-PERFORMANCE COMPUTING CENTER STUTTART (HLRS) (23)	DE
8. FUTURE NEEDS MANAGEMENT CONSULTING LTD (FN) (24)	CY

4.6. Articles

The project is expected to publish articles, describing in detail, its scientific progress on third-party websites. These articles can be published on the websites of similar projects, organizations with a common mission, or research institutes interested in the project. KPI: Aim for a total of 10 articles on third-party websites. Currently, the project has published

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four (4) articles. It is expected that the KPI will be achieved as the research and the activities of the project advance and give more results to share with the audience.

Table 4. List of Articles in 3rd party websites

Article Issue	Title	Contributor
1 st	CoE Hidalgo2 Urban Building Pilot at NumPEX workshop on Discretization@Exascale (25)	Cemosis
2 nd	Expanding Horizons: Ktirio and the Urban Building Vision in Hidalgo2 (26)	Cemosis
3 rd	CoE Hidalgo2: Urban Building Modeling (27)	Cemosis
4 th	First NumPEX/Exa-DI workshop on Efficient Discretisation for PDE@Exascale (28)	Cemosis

4.7. Communication on other platforms

- HiDALGO2 collaborates with CORDIS and is regularly in contact with the CORDIS publication team to provide updates about the progress of HiDALGO2 and promote our achievements.
- HiDALGO2 is uploading all Dissemination and Communication materials on the ZENODO platform (29)
- Upcoming platforms for the Dissemination of the project’s results:
- The HiDALGO2 consortium has recently decided to include an additional use case in their project results. After the General Assembly (GA) approves this change, the use cases will be finalized and made available on the project website as well as the **EOSC Portal Catalog & Marketplace** (30)

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5. Off-line dissemination tools

5.1. Printed promotional material

HiDALGO2 has created respective brochures and posters serving as promotional material which include key information on the project. They are shared in the project folder for all the partners to download, print and distribute in the events they join or organize.

Figure 13. HiDALGO2 poster

Figure 14. HiDALGO2 Factsheet

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Figure 15. Brochure downloads

All the above-mentioned materials have been uploaded on the ZENODO platform (see section 4.7), so the audience of the project can view and download them.

KPIs: The target is 250 downloads until December 2026 (M48) and 1500 flyers distributed in third-party events attended. **So far the project has achieved 96 downloads and 100 flyers distributed on EuroHPC Users Day until December 2023 (M12).**

Figure 16. HiDALGO2 materials distributed in EuroHPC Users Day

Specific printed material for events

The printed and online visual material necessary for third-party events and the Euro HPC Summit, is complimented when needed by additional material. The visuals are created by the dissemination team (Future Needs) and approved by the project coordinator and the partners. Specifically, a poster for the EuroHPC booth at the International Supercomputing Conference was designed at the very beginning of the project.

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Figure 17. Poster in EuroHPC booth in International Supercomputing Conference

5.2. Publications

No publications in open-access journals have been published by the HiDALGO2 consortium till the end of 2023. Regarding the peer-reviewed papers & popular science articles, it is expected that there will be submission and acceptance for publication of 25 articles, as the research and the activities of the project advance and give more results.

Before any publication in peer-reviewed journals, conference proceedings, etc. partners are requested to inform about their plans:

- the WP Leader, about the production of a paper related to their WP,
- the Dissemination WP Leader,
- the project Coordinator.

The process followed is thoroughly described in the Publications section of the deliverable D6.1 “Brand and Roadmap for Awareness Campaign”. In case the procedure is not followed, neither expenses nor effort associated with the production of the paper under discussion can be justified.

5.3. Conferences / external events / workshops

Our communication strategy includes a comprehensive engagement plan with external events and conferences. Initially, the consortium has pinpointed several key events, deemed highly relevant. This list of events is maintained in the project's shared drive, where all partners are encouraged to contribute with their suggestions.

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The objectives when the project partners participate in events, conferences, information days, workshops, etc. are to disseminate the project’s results and outputs. The partners are regularly (during the monthly dissemination meetings) advised to align when more than one consortium organization is participating in an event or conference, to maximize the benefits of the activity for the project.

Project partners are encouraged to focus on showcasing the project's aims, mission, and outcomes of various use cases to enhance project visibility and outreach. To support the project’s communication and digital presence, they are requested to provide photos from the events they participate in, featuring HiDALGO2 brochures, posters, presentations, or other related materials. These photos, are shared on HiDALGO2's social media (figure 18) and the news section of the project’s web page.

KPIs: Consortium partners will attend at least 30 conferences, trade shows, workshops, and networking activities with pertinent EU/national projects to maximize the dissemination and impact of the project. **By December 2023 (M12) HiDALGO2 has participated in 11 conferences.**

Table 5. List of Events attended and related articles on the HiDALGO2 website

Blog Issue	Release Month	Title	Contributor
1st	M2 (February 2023)	HiDALGO2 in CASTIEL2 Kick-off (31)	FN
2nd	M2 (February 2023)	HiDALGO2 in SIAM CSE (CSE23) (32)	Collaborative
3rd	M4 (April 2023)	EuroHPC Summit 2023 (33)	Collaborative
4th	M6 (June 2023)	HiDALGO2 in ISC 2023 (34)	Collaborative
5th	M10 (October 2023)	EuroHPC in Supercomputing Conference (SC23) (35)	Collaborative
6th	M10 (October 2023)	HiDALGO2 in ICIAM 2023, Japan, August 2023 (36)	Collaborative
7th	M11 (November 2023)	Challenges and bottlenecks of our Urban Building pilot at NumPEX workshop on Discretization @Exascale (37)	Collaborative
8th	M11 (November 2023)	A Workshop Uncertainty Quantification by HiDALGO2, SEAVEA, and CIRCE (38)	Collaborative
9th	M12 (December 2023)	Insights of SC23 in Denver (39)	Collaborative
10th	M12 (December 2023)	HiDALGO2 in Big Data Value Association’s Task Force meeting (40)	Collaborative
11th	M12 (December 2023)	HiDALGO2 at EuroHPC User Day in Brussels (41)	Collaborative

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The HiDALGO2 project is set to participate in several important upcoming conferences, which include the HiPEAC conference in January 2024 (M13), in Munich, with the joint workshop “Towards reliable Digital Twin: advancing applications and tools capabilities for Global Challenges”. More about the workshop can be found on the project’s website (42). Also, HiDALGO2 will have a display and exhibition at the EuroHPC Summit in March 2024. The process the project follows to monitor the progress is detailed in the 6.5 section of the D6.1 deliverable.

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6. Collaborations and Synergies

HiDALGO2 is actively cooperating with other **Centres of Excellence (CoEs)** as it happened previously in HIDALGO to develop a synergy effect. A relationship with **CASTIEL2** has been established to promote project competencies and services to industrial users. Another level of cooperation is **EOSC**. Facilitating access to HiDALGO2 services from the level of "**EOSC Portal Catalog & Marketplace**" will be another step towards the federalization of European resources and unification of access for a wider group of recipients.

HiDALGO2 is highly ambitious and to achieve its maximum potential it is linked with various actions with collaboration agreements, specifically the following:

- Plasma Exascale-Performance Simulations CoE - Pushing flagship plasma simulations codes to tackle exascale-enabled Grand Challenges via performance optimisation and codesign, Plasma-PEPSC, 101093261, funded by EUROHPC
- BioExcel Centre of Excellence for Computational Biomolecular Research, BioExcel-3, 101093290, funded by EUROHPC
- Center of Excellence for Exascale CFD, CEEC, 101093393, funded by EUROHPC
- Coordination and Support for National Competence Centres and Centres of Excellence on a European Level Phase 2, CASTIEL 2, 101102047, funded by EUROHPC
- Centre of Excellence in exascale-oriented application co-design and delivery for multiscale simulations, MultiXscale, 101093169, funded by EUROHPC
- Center of Excellence for Exascale in Solid Earth - Second Phase, ChEES-2P, 101093038, funded by EUROHPC
- Center of excellence for weather and climate phase 3, ESiWACE3, 101093054, funded by EUROHPC
- European Centre of Excellence for Engineering Applications on HPC and associated technologies, EXCELLERAT P2, 101092621, funded by EUROHPC
- Materials design at the eXascale, MaX, 101093374, funded by EUROHPC
- Scalable Parallel and distributed Astrophysical Codes for Exascale, SPACE, 101093441, funded by EUROHPC

In the project's repository, there is a list of proposed synergies, projects, bodies, networks, etc, where each partner can add relevant information.

Until December 2023 (M12) collaborations and joint actions achieved are the following. The project:

- Joined the kick-off meeting of CASTIEL2 in February 2023
- Joined the SIAM (Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics) Conference on Computational Science and Engineering (CSE) with a lecture in March 2023

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- Participated in the EuroHPC Summit 2023 by joining the panel of a workshop in March 2023
- Joint workshop on Uncertainty Quantification with SEAVEA, and CIRCE on November 2023
- Joint workshop Exa-DI on Efficient Discretization@Exascale with NUMPEX on November 2023

The stakeholders the consortium collaborated with were:

- CASTIEL2
- SIAM (Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics)
- EuroHPC
- SEAVEA (Software Environment for Actionable & VVUQ-evaluated Exascale Applications)
- CIRCE (Computational Immediate Response Centre for Emergencies)
- NUMPEX (Numeric for Exascale)

For more details regarding the events and workshops we collaborated in, see Table 5 above.

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7. Conclusions

The communication and dissemination activities remain a fundamental cornerstone of HiDALGO2 project. Thus, the report on the achievements during the first year of the project holds immense significance, as it offers a comprehensive overview of the results and proves that the strategies and additional actions planned to improve performance are in the right direction.

Reviewing the full roll-out of our social media strategy, the report shows the well-established online presence of the project, sharing updates and encouraging stakeholders' engagement. Keep following the strategic approach of differentiating communication and dissemination activities based on each project phase, ensuring targeted and impactful engagement. Thus, the D6.1 "Brand and Roadmap for Awareness Campaign" remains a solid foundation for dissemination to guide the HiDALGO2 consortium, ensuring that our project's outcomes reach the right audiences. It is updated by the new strategies added in this report and allows flexibility to adapt to the project phases.

Moreover, the dissemination of the upcoming results as the project advances as well as the additional strategies proposed (e.g. Campaigns on social media) are expected to optimize the communication and dissemination results and increase the impact of our efforts. Specific guidelines for the implementation of the new strategic tools introduced will be shared with the consortium to ensure effective engagement of the stakeholders and dissemination of the project outcomes.

Future Needs organizes & leads a monthly meeting, dedicated to the activities of the Dissemination and Communication work package, where all partners align on their contribution to the achievement of the KPIs listed below (see Table 6). Conclusions and agreed actions are included in the meeting minutes uploaded in the project's shared folder and shared through email with all partners. The WP6 regular meeting ensures that the consortium achievements are reviewed, and the partners can be supported more efficiently if needed.

Overall, the project consortium has made significant progress towards achieving the dissemination and communication KPIs set for the project. Especially after September 2023 (M09) and the corrective actions taken as mentioned in the above sections of this report, the project's KPIs performance has increased significantly. The biggest challenge faced in terms of communication and dissemination was the slow growth of the newsletter subscribers and the website audience. To address that, several factors were considered, and actions were taken to ensure improved performance and achievement of our KPIs. Networking on the social media channels with important initiatives in the sector by the dissemination leaders will be continued and intensified as Task 6.4 "Awareness Creation, Collaboration and Community Support" will progress and a community will be developed. The clustering event planned for the next year is also expected to contribute to the growth

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of the project's audience. Moreover, the social media campaigns planned will increase engagement, and the creation of a user-friendly newsletter and its promotion to our community stakeholders in the future is expected to further broaden the project's impact. As a consortium, we are committed to constantly improving as the projects produce more and more results. We remain dedicated to making significant strides in research and dissemination, aiming to achieve the maximum impact and fulfil the project objectives by its conclusion.

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References

1. HiDALGO2 Press Release . [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/pressrelease1/> .
2. HiDALGO2 Project Started. [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/hidalgo2-project-started/>.
3. HiDALGO2 – EXCELLERAT P2 joint mini symposium at the SIAM CSE23 conference . [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/hidalgo2-excellerat-p2-joint-mini-symposium-at-the-siam-cse23-conference>.
4. Meet the HiDALGO2 partner Cemosis: Strasbourg Modeling and Simulation Center . [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/meet-the-hidalgo2-partner-cemosis-strasbourg-modeling-and-simulation-center/>.
5. The QCG-portal and HiDALGO2 . [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/the-qcg-portal-and-hidalgo2/>.
6. Uncertainty Quantification in HiDALGO2: Enhancing Modeling Credibility for Environmental Pilots . [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/uncertainty-quantification-in-hidalgo2-enhancing-modeling-credibility-for-environmental-pilots/>.
7. Trying to decode the wildfires’ behavior. [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/trying-to-decode-the-wildfires-behavior/>.
8. Data analytics, AI, and visualisation in the HiDALGO2 project . [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/data-analytics-ai-and-visualisation-in-the-hidalgo2-project/>.
9. HiDALGO2 Adopts DevOps and CI/CD for Seamless Supercomputer Deployments . [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/hidalgo2-adopts-devops-and-ci-cd-for-seamless-supercomputer-deployments>.
10. Newsletter Issue 1st. [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/newsletter1/>.
11. Newsletter Issue 2nd. [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/newsletter2/>.
12. Newsletter Issue 1st (LinkedIn). [Online] https://www.linkedin.com/posts/hidalgo2-project_newsletter-1-hidalgo2-activity-7072486297658957825-2smB?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop.
13. Newsletter Issue 2nd (LinkedIn). [Online] <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7125519366757961728/>.
14. Newsletter Issue 1st (X). [Online] https://twitter.com/HiDALGO2_EU/status/1666722250492375042.
15. Newsletter Issue 2nd (X). [Online] https://twitter.com/HiDALGO2_EU/status/1719754673324781943.
16. Newsletter Issue 1st (Facebook). [Online] <https://www.facebook.com/EU.Project.HiDALGO/posts/pfbid0pGMA3WvPC79Kkh3JTYi1ACRvyZBMfF1toGZ7bNgy6oVhPDtyQf7QenfJCkX3BTKkl&sa=D&source=docs&ust=1705667685306985&usg=AOvVaw3GH11IYpGB2Rge7zGbYP7U>.

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17. Newsletter Issue 2nd (Facebook). [Online]
<https://www.facebook.com/EU.Project.HiDALGO/posts/pfbid02c8hwAWGJGz6byFw954m3fZFeVBds6bZCNiQ9R3YaoWhU7A6T4TFkxog9hUSGLCwPI>.
18. Twitter: @HiDALGO2_EU. [Online] https://twitter.com/HiDALGO2_EU.
19. LinkedIn: HiDALGO2 Project. [Online]
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/HiDALGO2/>.
20. YouTube:@HiDALGO2. [Online]
<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCajli2XMTsQRDMKcvgvoaAg>.
21. Facebook:Hidalgo2 EU Project. [Online]
<https://www.facebook.com/EU.Project.HiDALGO>.
22. INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK (PCNS). [Online] <https://www.psn.pl/projects/hidalgo2/>.
23. HIGH- PERFORMANCE COMPUTING CENTER STUTTGART (HLRS). [Online]
<https://www.hlrs.de/projects/detail/hidalgo2>.
24. FUTURE NEEDS MANAGEMENT CONSULTING LTD (FN). [Online]
<https://futureneeds.eu/case-studies/hidalgo2/>.
25. CoE Hidalgo2 Urban Building Pilot at NumPEX workshop on Discretization@Exascale . [Online] <https://github.com/orgs/feelpp/discussions/2188>.
26. Expanding Horizons: Ktirio and the Urban Building Vision in Hidalgo2. [Online]
<https://github.com/orgs/feelpp/discussions/2167> .
27. CoE Hidalgo2: Urban Building Modeling . [Online]
<https://github.com/orgs/feelpp/discussions/2112> .
28. First NumPEX/Exa-DI workshop on Efficient Discretisation for PDE@Exascale. [Online] <https://github.com/orgs/feelpp/discussions/2187> .
29. ZENODO Platform. [Online]
https://zenodo.org/search?q=metadata.creators.person_or_org.name%3A%22HiDALGO2%22&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=bestmatch.
30. EOSC Portal Catalog & Marketplace. [Online] <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-in-practice/open-call>.
31. HiDALGO2 in CASTIEL2 Kick-off. [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/hidalgo2-in-castiel2-%ce%baick-off/>.
32. HiDALGO2 in SIAM CSE (CSE23). [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/hidalgo2-in-siam-cse-cse23/> .
33. EuroHPC Summit 2023. [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/eurohpc-summit-2023/> .
34. HiDALGO2 in ISC 2023 . [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/hidalgo2-in-isc-2023/>.
35. EuroHPC in Supercomputing Conference (SC23). [Online]
<https://www.hidalgo2.eu/eurohpc-in-supercomputing-conference-sc23/> .
36. HiDALGO2 in ICIAM 2023, Japan, August 2023. [Online]
<https://www.hidalgo2.eu/hidalgo2-in-iciam-2023-japan-august-2023/> .

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- 37. Challenges and bottlenecks of our Urban Building pilot at NumPEX workshop on Discretization @Exascale . [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/challenges-and-bottlenecks-of-our-urban-building-pilot-at-numpex-workshop-on-discretization-exascale/> .
- 38. A Workshop Uncertainty Quantification by HiDALGO2, SEAVEA, and CIRCE . [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/a-workshop-uncertainty-quantification-by-hidalgo2-seavea-and-circe/> .
- 39. Insights of SC23 in Denver. [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/insights-of-sc23-in-denver/> .
- 40. HiDALGO2 in Big Data Value Association’s Task Force meeting . [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/hidalgo2-in-big-data-value-associations-task-force-meeting/> .
- 41. HiDALGO2 at EuroHPC User Day in Brussels. [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/hidalgo2-at-eurohpc-user-day-in-brussels/> .
- 42. HiPEAC conference in January 2024 (M13), in Munich, with the joint workshop “Towards reliable Digital Twin: advancing applications and tools capabilities for Global Challenges”. [Online] <https://www.hidalgo2.eu/joint-workshop-hidalgo-in-hipeac/> .

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Annex

Below table presents of all KPIs progress until December 2023 (M12):

Table 6. KPIs Report Table

KPI Title	KPI measure	Goal	Achieved
Website	# of unique visitors	8000	666
Visual Identity	N/A	N/A	N/A
Press Releases	# of press releases	2	1
Newsletters	# of subscribers	600	58
	# of newsletters	12	2
Project Factsheet	# of downloads	250	98
	# of sheets distributed	1500	100
Presentations at third party events	# of events attended	30	11
Peer-reviewed papers & popular science articles	# of publications of articles	25	0
	# of blog posts	46	8
	# of articles in 3rd party websites	10	4
Social Media	# of LinkedIn followers	1500	224
	# of Twitter followers	1000	434
	# of likes in Twitter & LinkedIn	5000	1975
HiDALGO2 Workshops & Clustering Event	#of stakeholders in the advisory board	15	5
	# of stakeholders engaged in project activities	10	6
	# of attendees of the clustering event	60	N/A

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